

Low temperature processed perovskite solar cell fabricated from pre-synthesized CsFAPbI₃ powder

M. P. U. Haris^a, Samrana Kazim^{a,b}, Shahzada Ahmad^{*a,b}

^aBCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures,
UPV/EHU Science Park, 48940 Leioa, Spain

Tel: +34 946128811 Email:shahzada.ahmad@bcmaterials.net

^bIKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, 48009, Spain

Abstract

Investigating methylammonium (MA) and bromide (Br) -free perovskite structure is paramount to reduce thermal diffusion and phase segregation which has plagued rapid development of perovskite solar cells. Such engineered compositions are intrinsically stable and compatible with single and multi-junction solar cells. We demonstrate a δ -phase free formamidinium based solar cells, derived from a powder perovskite precursor with Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}PbI₃ fabricated at a modest temperature of 80 °C, to yield a competitive performance >17% with a negligible hysteresis. Importantly, these fabricated PSCs show enhanced stability and efficiency over the conventional FAPbI₃ which demands high temperature (150 °C) processing for solar cells fabrication. We put forward a strategy for substantial materials synthesis, which can be effectively processable at low temperature.

Keywords: perovskite solar cells, FAPbI₃, charge transport, electro-optical properties.

Introduction

The rapid unprecedented improvements in the power conversion efficiency (PCE) from mere 3.8 to 25.5% in just a decade boosted solution processed hybrid lead halide perovskite as a promising light harvester for photovoltaics (PVs).¹⁻³ Methylammonium lead iodide (MAPbI₃) perovskite based solar cells enjoy the privilege of intense investigation owing to its high PCE value, though also represents severe intrinsic degradation of perovskite under light, moisture, heat and oxygen that impeded its rapid commercial aspects. Recently, the formamidinium lead iodide (FAPbI₃) are attracting significant attention due to its lower band gap of ~1.48eV, and possibility of strong secondary hydrogen bond formation with PbI₆ octahedra along with higher thermal stability, as compared to thermally unstable MAPbI₃ or mixed halide perovskites which display phase segregation. Notably, FAPbI₃ are photostable as compared to MAPbI₃. However, FAPbI₃ undergoes polymorphic transformation from photoactive black α -phase (~1.48 eV) to inactive yellow δ -phase (~2.43 eV) at room temperature. Moreover, α -FAPbI₃ phase is thermodynamically unstable below 150 °C and its degradation to FAI and PbI₂ starts at the similar temperature⁴⁻⁸, which makes use of FAPbI₃ in perovskite solar cells (PSC) challenging. Strategies have been developed to overcome such issues in recent years. The most common methods are the alloying at FA site with small cations such as, methylammonium (MA⁺), Cesium (Cs⁺), rubidium (Rb⁺), potassium (K⁺) and addition of large organic cations to form 2D/3D mixed phases.⁹⁻¹⁵ Initial reports showed the introduction of MA to form a mixed perovskites (MAPbBr₃)_x (FAPbI₃)_{1-x} to enhance PCE, phase stability and lower the transition temperature to 100 °C. Triple cation based mixed perovskites (MA, FA and Cs) was reported to improve the PSC performance. In a seminal work, Gratzel et. al showed methylammonium thiocyanate vapour assisted conversion of δ - FAPbI₃ to the desired α -phase. The strong affinity of Pb²⁺ ions with the

surface thiocyanate anions induce the disintegration of δ - phase at the top surface and penetration of MA^+ into the PbI_6 chains which eventually stabilise the α -phase and gave high performance.¹⁶ However, the volatile nature of MA hinders the long-term stability of devices.¹⁷ Thus MA-free, low temperature processed and phase pure α -FAPbI₃ will be the promising candidate for long term stable PSCs. The fabrication of δ/α phase junction $\text{Cs}_{0.2}\text{FA}_{0.8}\text{PbI}_3$ films at 60 °C¹⁸ PSCs fabricated with $\text{Cs}_x\text{FA}_{(1-x)}\text{PbI}_3$ film at 100 °C gave a PCE of 15.7%.¹² Moreover, phase stabilization with high device performance at 85 °C was achieved with the addition of PbS quantum dots.^{19,20} Although, improved phase stability was reported, the device stability remained unaddressed. Compositional engineering at FA site induces structural distortions and relaxation of lattice strain through a strain-compensation strategy was observed by introducing smaller and larger ions together with a certified PCE of 24.4%.²¹

Pre-synthesized FAPbI₃ powder as precursor over the conventional route stemmed device long-term stability and can reduce device hysteresis by suppressing the trap states.²²⁻²⁴ Precursor engineering with the perovskite single crystals or powders over the commercially available cost ineffective materials will reduce the manufacturing cost of PSCs without affecting their performance. In the past, MAPbX_3 (X=Br, Cl or I) single crystals and powders were employed as the precursor and the fabricated PSCs demonstrated reproducibility and reduced interfacial trap density.^{25,26} Recently, improved stability and device performance with δ -FAPbI₃ powder perovskite precursor synthesized at room temperature precipitation method over the conventional method was explored.²² To address such challenges, we undertook the synthesis of MA, Br-free, Cs amalgamated δ -FAPbI₃ powder perovskite precursor employing low-grade PbI₂ (99%), process at room temperature and annealing at 80 °C. Further, Cs inclusion in FAPbI₃ powder perovskite precursor can extend the longevity significantly. The fabricated PSCs performed

competitively and gave a PCE of >17%, as compared to their conventional counterparts, while adopting milder synthetic protocol.

Results and discussion

We synthesized non-perovskite δ -Cs_xFA_(1-x)PbI₃ powder through precipitation method, for this CsI and FAI was dissolved in acetonitrile in varying ratios. Yellow colour perovskite powder (yield 92%) was precipitated by the employment of low-grade PbI₂ followed by 24 hr stirring (Figure S1). The complete removal of acetonitrile was ensured by vacuum drying the precipitation for 24 hr. The high Cs concentration impose larger distortions to perovskite lattice and thereby inhibits the PV performance,¹² to eliminate such behaviour we limited the concentration to $x \leq 0.1$. The phase purity of synthesized powders was monitored by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique. Figure 1a illustrates the diffractograms of synthesized δ -FAPbI₃ and δ -Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}PbI₃ powders at room temperature and compared with the diffractograms of δ -CsPbI₃²⁵. The diffraction peaks at (010), (011), (-120), (002), (012), (021), (-122), (-130), (022) and (240) indicates the hexagonal non-perovskite δ -phase of FAPbI₃. The absence of α -FAPbI₃ and δ -CsPbI₃ peaks signal the phase purity of synthesized powders. The noted blue shift in the diffraction patterns of δ -Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}PbI₃ suggests increase in the inter-planar distance, this was also validated by the absence of any additional peak. This point towards the structural incorporation of Cs into the δ -FAPbI₃ powder. We carried out the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements for both non-perovskite powders and identified the elemental composition and the nature of their chemical bonding. The survey spectrum and signals from core levels are presented (Figure 1b and Figure S2a-c). The signals from Cs 3d core level (Figure 1b) for both samples are the characteristic peaks at 721.8 eV and 735.77 eV corresponding to Cs 3d_{5/2} and Cs 3d_{3/2} respectively, only visible in δ -Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}PbI₃. It can be deduced that the shift in the binding energy (Figure S2b-c), of

Pb 4f and I 3d core level signals, emerge from the Cs inclusion.²⁷ We attribute the shift of Pb 4f peaks towards higher binding energy to the increase in the cationic charge of Pb ions, which is also evident from the diffractograms.

Figure 1. a) Diffractograms of synthesized non-perovskite powders, b) XPS core level signals from Cs 3d and c) schematic illustration of thin film fabrication procedure for FAPI-150 and CsFAPI-80 perovskites.

The influence of Cs on the phase transition temperature (δ to α conversion), was systematically probed by means of in-situ XRD analysis for non-perovskite powders (Figure 2) and ex-situ XRD analysis of perovskite thin layers at variable temperatures. For the *in-situ* temperature dependent XRD analysis, the powders were gradually heated from 30 °C – 150 °C at a rate of 2 °C / minute. The diffractograms depicts the

characteristic peaks for α -phase at $\sim 14^\circ$ (100) and $\sim 28^\circ$ (200), which emerge at 130°C for $\delta\text{-Cs}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ powder while in the case of control samples ($\delta\text{-FAPbI}_3$), it appears at 150°C . These are in agreement with reports dealing with Cs incorporation into perovskite suggests lowering of phase transition temperature.¹² The smaller ionic radius of Cs than FA cation helps to reduce the Goldschmidt tolerance factor from 1.04 to ideal range and thus induces phase stability at moderately lower temperature. Similarly, $\delta\text{-Cs}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ powder undergoes phase transition at lower temperature compared to its FA analogue. Arguably, the lower transition temperature of developed $\delta\text{-Cs}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ powder can be employed in the defect-tolerant, solvent-free vacuum-processed perovskite solar cells from a single source instead of widely used multi-sourced co-sublimation, further these powders can be synthesized on large scale easily.

Figure 2: *In situ* diffractograms for a) $\delta\text{-FAPbI}_3$ and b) $\delta\text{-Cs}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ powders respectively. Samples were heated from $30 - 150^\circ\text{C}$ at $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

To decipher the phase transition temperature, XRD studies of thin films deposited at varied temperatures (Figure 3a, b) was carried out. Yellow non-perovskite powders were dissolved in DMF:DMSO mixture (4:1) and the solution was stirred for 3 hr to complete the dissolution. The spin coated thin films were annealed at varying temperatures for 20 minutes and the corresponding diffractograms were acquired (Figure 1c). FAPbI_3 films

were annealed at 60, 100 and 150 °C (Figure 3a) and we noted the formation of α -FAPbI₃ phase only at 150 °C, and below 150 °C it only represents the δ -FAPbI₃ signature diffractions (010) and (002). XRD spectra of Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}PbI₃ films annealed at 25, 60, 80, 100 and 150 °C are shown (Figure 2b). At RT, we noted diffractions corresponding to δ -phase at (002), (014) and a weak diffraction corresponding to α -phase at (111). i.e. Cs incorporation enables the phase transition from room temperature to form a δ/α phase junction where the major proportion is from δ -FAPbI₃. The shifting of the diffraction angle (2Φ) in FAPbI₃ can be due to the expansion and contraction of the lattice. This also signals the incorporation of Cs⁺ into the lattice of FAPbI₃ to form a solid-state alloy. The diffraction peak at 12.8° indicates the presence of excess PbI₂. By annealing at 60 °C, (111) diffraction peak becomes intense and (100), (110), (200) and (210) diffractions also emerge. The presence of weak (002) diffraction specifies the formation of δ/α phase junction with a major fraction of α -phase. The diffraction peaks for δ -FAPbI₃ disappeared and highly oriented α -FAPbI₃ phase was formed by annealing at 80 °C. This shifting of the diffraction angle can be due to the expansion and contraction of the lattice. This also signals the incorporation of Cs⁺ into the lattice of FAPbI₃ to form a solid-state alloy. We noted a weaker diffraction peak at ~ 110 , signalling the presence of FAI.²⁸ The trivial amounts of PbI₂ and FAI will improve the crystal quality by passivating the grain boundaries and vacancies.^{29,30} δ -FAPbI₃ phase remains fully inhibited even at high temperatures. Notably, we observed a difference in preferential orientation for low temperature processed films (LT \leq 60 °C) and high temperature processed films (HT \geq 80 °C). HT films have the strong diffractions from (hko) planes while the low temperature films show diffractions from the (hkl) planes. Arguably, these infers that strongly textured δ -phase free perovskite can be formed from 80 °C.

The powder diffractograms (Figure S3) of FAPbI_3 at 150 °C (FAPI-150), $\text{Cs}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ fabricated at 80 °C (CsFAPI-80) and 150 °C (CsFAPI-150) was recorded. We observed the δ -phase (010) diffraction in FAPbI_3 disappeared on Cs incorporation. The diffraction peak intensities are higher for $\text{Cs}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ as compared to the FAPbI_3 film. The (100) diffractions of above three cases are compared in the inset. The full width at half maximum (FWHM) decreases from 0.24° to 0.11° and to 0.10° for FAPI-150, CsFAPI-80 and CsFAPI-150 respectively. The increase in relative intensity of diffraction peaks and narrowing of FWHM indicates the higher crystallinity. It is in agreement with the previous reports of Cs induced crystallinity enhancement in perovskites.³¹ Microstructure analysis was made by performing scanning electron microscopy (SEM) experiments (Figure 3d-f). Large area uniformity in the microstructure can be inferred, while the inset represents images at a scale bar of 500 nm to gaze the crystallinity and grain size. It can be deduced from the micrographs that Cs insertion reduces the grain boundaries, grain size and pinholes, while inducing higher crystallinity. The employment of Cs increases density of crystal nuclei in the film formation, this in turn reduces the grain size and the absence of agglomeration of crystallites enhances the perovskite crystallinity.³² Grain size increment refers to higher crystallinity and the presence of PbI_2 was noted for CsFAPI-150 as compared to CsFAPI-80, in agreement with PXRD data (Figure S2). UV-Visible absorption spectra and the steady state photoluminescence spectra was measure to deduce the changes in absorption and fluorescence (Figure 3c), and the bandgap was calculated from the tauc plot (Figure S4). The FAPbI_3 shows a strong PL intensity with a peak centred at 816 nm, and Cs incorporation induces blue shift in the emission (809 and 805 nm for CsFAPI-80 and CsFAPI-150), an increment in the bandgap and the absorption coefficient.²⁸ The higher blue shifting in the fluorescence spectra of CsFAPI-150 than of CsFAPI-80 is attributed to the passivated trap states on the surface or of the grain

boundaries, or associated with the concentration of Cs. High temperature (150 °C) annealing structurally incorporate more Cs ions into FAPbI₃, also supported by the shifted (100) diffraction peak (Figure 3).

Further we have studied the influence of Cs concentration, where FAPbI₃ and Cs_xFA_(1-x)PbI₃ (x = 0.5, 1) films were annealed at 150 and 80 °C respectively (Figure S5). On varying the x = 0 – 0.1, the δ-phase (010) gradually disappears and the PbI₂ phase becomes weaker. High phase purity and low annealing temperature of CsFAPI-80 allows low temperature processed solar cells employing FAPbI₃ and the choice of the substrates.

Figure 3. a-b) XRD measurements for perovskite thin films annealed at different temperatures, a) FAPbI₃ films and b) Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}PbI₃ films. The reflections indicated by * and # represent Bragg reflections associated with FAI and PbI₂, respectively. c) normalized UV-Vis absorption and steady-state photoluminescence spectra of FAPI-150 (black), CsFAPI-80 (red) and CsFAPI-150 (blue) perovskite films. d-f) top view of SEM images of perovskite films d) FAPI-150, e) CsFAPI-80 and f) CsFAPI-150; The insets are the corresponding zoom-in images with a scale bar of 500 nm.

To unravel the merits of the synthesized perovskites powder, PSCs was fabricated using a device architecture of FTO/c-TiO₂/SnO₂-QD/perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au. Firstly, the device parameters with pre-synthesized perovskite powder-based PSCs was evaluated

and the corresponding device statistics are summarised (Figure S 6 and Table S1-S3). The pristine FAPI-150 based PSCs gave an average PCE of 13.196% (± 1.56) with an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 912.06 (± 17.06) mV, short-circuit current (J_{sc}) of 22.22 (± 0.55) mAcm^{-2} and fill factor (FF) of 65.04% (± 6.63) and the Cs incorporation boosted the efficiency of CsFAPI-150 to 15.14% (± 1.22) with V_{oc} of 959.39 (± 15.7) mV, J_{sc} of 22.41 (± 0.57) mAcm^{-2} and FF of 70.43% (± 5.22). Remarkably, the champion device fabricated from CsFAPI-80 absorber layer gave the average PCE of 16.75 % (± 0.32) with a V_{oc} of 1005.7 (± 23.2) mV, J_{sc} of 22.16 (± 0.21) mAcm^{-2} and FF of 75.20% (± 2.06). J - V characteristics (Figure 4a) under AM 1.5G illumination for devices with PCE of 15.01% ($V_{oc} = 912.7\text{mV}$, $J_{sc} = 22.75 \text{ mAcm}^{-2}$, FF = 72.30%), 16.60% ($V_{oc} = 965 \text{ mV}$, $J_{sc} = 22.71 \text{ mAcm}^{-2}$, FF = 75.73) and 17.11% ($V_{oc} = 1000 \text{ mV}$, $J_{sc} = 22.00 \text{ mAcm}^{-2}$, FF = 77.76%) for FAPI-150, CsFAPI-150 and CsFAPI-80 respectively are presented. The significant increment in V_{oc} and FF contributes to the enhancement of the PCE with Cs inclusion. The series (R_s) and shunt resistance (R_{sh}) calculated from the inverse slope near zero J_{sc} and V_{oc} region respectively, can influence the V_{oc} and FF .²⁴ Pristine FAPI-150 showed a higher value of R_s ($5.03 \text{ }\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$) and the incorporation of Cs^+ into the lattice of FAPbI_3 (to form a solid state alloy) decreases in the case of CsFAPI-150 ($3.86 \text{ }\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$). A slightly lower R_s value was noted for CsFAPI-80 ($3.25 \text{ }\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$), which can be ascribed due to presence of lower defects sites at the surface and was supported by PV and electrical measurements. Apparently, R_{sh} showed by FAPI-150 ($2.02 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$) increases to 3.64 and $7.27 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ for CsFAPI-150 and CsFAPI-80 respectively. The V_{oc} and FF increment in CsFAPI-80 is attributed to the 35.4% and 23.3% decline in R_s and $\sim 400\%$ and $\sim 200\%$ increase in R_{sh} over FAPI-150 and CsFAPI-150 respectively. We calculated the hysteresis index (Table 1 and Figure S7) using the standard equation,³³ Cs incorporation lower the hysteresis, notably CsFAPI-80 exhibited a lower (0.02) than CsFAPI-150 (0.06).

Table 1. J - V parameters for the best performing PSCs fabricated through powder method.

Samples		V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mAcm^{-2})	FF (%)	PCE (%)	R_s ($\Omega.\text{cm}^2$)	R_{sh} ($\text{k}\Omega.\text{cm}^2$)	HI
FAP1-150	RS	0.913	22.75	72.30	15.01	5.03	2.02	
	FS	0.913	22.55	63.82	13.13	6.96	1.60	
	Average	0.913	22.65	68.06	14.07			0.15
CsFAP1-80	RS	1.000	22.00	77.76	17.11	3.25	7.27	
	FS	1.014	22.05	73.69	16.47	4.03	2.85	
	Average	1.007	22.02	75.72	16.79			0.02
CsFAP1-150	RS	0.965	22.71	75.73	16.60	3.86	3.64	
	FS	0.969	22.63	69.97	15.34	4.35	1.03	
	Average	0.967	22.67	72.85	15.97			0.06

Spectral dependence of the external quantum efficiencies (EQEs) for the fabricated PSCs displayed a similar trend and flat response in the spectra of 450-700 nm range was deduced (Figure 4c). The usage of same charge selective layers, gave similar EQEs of >80%, in agreement with the UV-Vis absorption spectra. CsFAP1-80 showed moderately lower EQE response at lower wavelength, and a slightly higher EQE (>85%) at 450-700nm be attributed to improved film quality. The EQEs and the band off set signals the lower recombination. The calculated integrated J_{SC} estimated from EQE data (Figure 4b) are 21.79, 22.14 and 21.40 mAcm^{-2} for FAP1-150, CsFAP1-80 and CsFAP1-150 respectively, are in accordance with the J_{SC} obtained from J - V measurements. On comparing the effect of annealing temperature of perovskite layers on the device performance, we infer that the low temperature processed CsFAP1-80 (80 °C) is higher than CsFAP1-150 (150 °C). They can be synthesized in large scale in powder form to unify the results or for its commercial endeavour.

Reduced performance from conventional FAPbI₃ was reported due to the poor interface and higher trap densities than the powder analogue which ultimately lowers the V_{OC} and FF .²³ To decipher the advantages of powder method over the conventional method of Cs incorporated FAPbI₃, we compared the PSCs fabricated through conventional method employing similar grade PbI₂ (99%), and the J - V characteristics are presented (Figure S8, Table S4-S5). The best performing PSCs from conventional method showed lower PCE of 12.62% ($V_{OC} = 875.7$ mV, $J_{SC} = 22.71$ mAcm⁻², $FF = 63.46\%$), 15.18% ($V_{OC} = 883.50$ mV, $J_{SC} = 23.17$ mAcm⁻², $FF = 73.83\%$) and 14.03% ($V_{OC} = 934.8$ mV, $J_{SC} = 21.59$ mAcm⁻², $FF = 69.52\%$) for FAPI-150, CsFAPI-150 and CsFAPI-80 respectively. In all the configurations, V_{OC} and FF decreases significantly as compared to our developed powder method. High V_{oc} deficit of 81.5 and 65.2 mV for conventional CsFAPI-150 and CsFAPI-80 respectively from their powder analogues are attributed to poor interface.²³ Arguably, it can be concluded that the powder method is superior over the conventional method to fabricate the MA, Br-free PSCs that can also be processable at low temperature.

We performed thermal admittance spectroscopy at varying temperature to reveal the shallow and deep defect density and trap energy distribution within the band gap of CsFAPbI₃ based PSCs.^{34,35} Briefly, dark capacitance-frequency (C - f) measurements were measured at different temperatures on the CsFAPbI₃ based fabricated PSCs from pre-synthesized powder without applying bias voltage (Figure S9 and S10). The frequency (f) ranges from 20 to 10⁶ Hz. The trap density of state (t_{DOS}) and energy distribution at room temperature can be derived from the frequency dependent capacitance measurement³⁶ and the detailed procedure can be found in the Supporting Information (Figures S9–S11). Figure 4c shows the extracted trap density profile (t_{DOS}) as a function of frequency-related energy (E_{ω}) for CsFAPI-80 and CsFAPI-150.

Figure 4. a) $J-V$ curve for FAPI-150, CsFAPI-80 and CsFAPI-150 PSCs fabricated through powder method measured under AM 1.5G 1 sun illumination, b) corresponding IPCE spectra and integrated currents, c) calculated trap density of state (N_T) at RT (25 °C) of CsFAPbI₃ based perovskite solar cells, i.e., CsFAPI-80 and CsFAPI-150 and d) normalized PCE for 1000 s of continuous MPP tracking under operational condition at ambient atmosphere.

In both types of devices, the trap density profile (t_{DOS}) shows the broad distribution with two peak maximums at lower and higher energies. In CsFAPI-150 based devices the peak maximum of t_{DOS} ($1.175 \times 10^{17} \text{ eV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-3}$) was found at $E_\omega = 0.119$ eV which shifts toward lower energy regimes and shows maximum at 0.053 eV in CsFAPI-80 based devices with almost similar value of t_{DOS} ($1.579 \times 10^{17} \text{ eV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-3}$).

Further t_{DOS} profile of CsFAPI-150 based devices showed another Gaussian peak at higher energy around 0.34 eV which corresponds to deeper defect states with a density of $1.32 \times 10^{18} \text{ eV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-3}$. In case of CsFAPI-80, onset of this high energy second Gaussian

peak noted at 0.29 eV. The trap density of state peak near to 0.119 eV is generally ascribed to the shallow defects near to valence band edge, while peak at >0.3 eV corresponds to deeper defect in CsFAPbI₃, which shows similar value of CsFAPbI₃. The shift of t_{DOS} towards lower energy in CsFAPI-80 devices signals that the charge carriers captured by these traps near to the valence band edge can be thermally activated and participate in the charge transportation and extraction, which leads to improvement in V_{oc} and FF for CsFAPI-80 based devices.

The fabricated PSCs were kept at maximum power point (MPP) tracking under operational conditions (continuous 1 sun illumination under 40-45% relative humidity at room temperature) (Figure 4d). The CsFAPI-80 and CsFAPI-150 based devices retained ~100% whereas FAPI-150 showed decrement from their original PCEs after 1000s. The fast response and stable output signal efficient charge extraction with trivial charge accumulation. The achieved device stability with CsFAPI supports the merit of pre-synthesized powder based PSCs, and choice of substrates for CsFAPI-80. We noted the stability of PSCs fabricated through conventional PSCs was significantly lowered as compared to the devices fabricated through powder method under MPP tracking (Figure S12).

Conclusion

To summarize, we demonstrated room-temperature synthesis of MA and Br-free, δ -Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}PbI₃ powder perovskite precursor from low-grade PbI₂ (99%) and fabricated the perovskite solar cells. The fabricated devices gave fast response, lower hysteresis value and a 100% PCE retainment under MPP tracking for 1000s along with a competitive power conversion efficiency in excess of 17%. The Cs alloying resulted in a δ -phase free, perovskite absorber fabricated at a temperature as low as 80 °C. The low temperature

annealing will prevent the perovskite from degradation and push perovskites solar cells towards cost-effective large-scale production and can adapt roll-to-roll manufacturing process on flexible substrates.

Author Contributions

M.P.U. H. made the experiments, fabricated the devices and prepared the initial draft, S.K. performed all the electro-optical measurements and analyse the data, S.A. supervised and directed the research.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Supplementary information

Detailed experimental procedures, Scheme, detailed XPS spectra, X-ray diffractograms, device statistics, admittance spectroscopy and steady state device performance.

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